

emergence, followed by the range – 1.5 to 2.0 bars.

Safri 17 germination at all depths and soil moisture levels was better than that of IR36.

Although farmers who direct seed their fields usually plant seeds deeper than normal to have good seedling emergence at the onset of the monsoon, our results show that increasing the planting depth of rice varieties sensitive to seed placement depth can adversely affect seedling emergence. Therefore, appropriate seeding depth for the variety to be planted should be practiced. □

Emergence dynamics of Safri 17 and IR36 as influenced by depth of water application and seeding depth.

Response of rice to zinc and sulfur

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Zn and S deficiencies are major constraints to irrigated rice in the Joyertek (Joydebpur) boro project area of Bangladesh. We evaluated Zn and S deficiency in a farmer field at Joyertek in 1983 boro with IR8 as the test variety. Soil was sandy loam with pH 7.6, 30 ppm available S (Ca-P extractable), and 0.6 ppm available Zn (0.05 NHC1 extractable). All plots received the recommended 60-9-17 kg NPK/ha. ZnSO₄ and zinc oxysulfate at 10 kg/ha were applied to Zn-treated plots. For S, 200 kg gypsum/ha

was applied. Both were broadcast and incorporated 4 wk after transplanting, when nutrient deficiencies were visible. Symptoms were brown spots and rusty streaks on the leaves, very poor growth, and light yellowing. Plants were harvested 7 wk after treatment. Chemical analysis and dry matter yield are in the table.

Applying gypsum and Zn in two forms dramatically increased the dry matter yield of IR8 as compared with the control. Deficiency symptoms disappeared in Zn-treated plots 2-3 wk after treatment. ZnSO₄ performed better than zinc oxysulfate. Plant analysis for Zn (1N HCl extraction) showed that plant Zn concentration in treated plots was still below the critical level, although it was relatively higher than in the control plots. Although

S concentration (nitric-perchloric acid digestion) and N:S were satisfactory, applying gypsum also improved rice growth. □

Effect of N, P, and K on available P and K in sodic soil

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We evaluated the effect of N, P, and K on available P and K in soil and on rice and wheat yields in a long-term field experiment on a partially reclaimed sodic soil at Karnal.

The soil was naturally highly sodic, but 3 yr (1971-74) of cropping and gypsum amendments had reduced pH to 9.2 and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) to 32.0 in the 0.15 cm surface layer of soil. Soil was 24% clay, 24% silt, and 52% sand, with 8.8 meq cation exchange capacity/100 g, 2.75% CaCO₃, 225 kg available N/ha, 0.25% organic carbon, 15.0 ppm available P, and 160 ppm K.

The 1974-82 experiment had eight treatments (Table 1) and was in a ran-

Effect of Zn and S on the performance of IR8 at Joyertek, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Dry matter yield (g/m ²)	Total Zn (ppm)	Total S (%)	Total N (%)	N:S
Control	63	16	.250	1.96	7.8
ZnSO ₄	554	25	.159	1.30	8.2
Zinc oxysulfate	112	19	.237	1.98	8.4
Gypsum	163	18	.219	1.58	7.2